

Online Communities of Practice: The Case of the Greek Ubuntu Community

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Abstract

The present article investigates the case of the Greek Ubuntu Community and analyzes its characteristics, based on the Five-Stage Model of Online Learning (Online Communities of Practice) by Gilly Salmon. In the above case study, the macroscopic developmental stages of an authentic Community of Practice as well as its interactions for construction of knowledge and for online learning are highlighted. In addition, the role of various online tools and social media in the above learning context is explored. Systematic analysis of the transitional stages of the examined Community, highlights the main characteristics of its structure and function, that effectively contribute to online learning, which, in turn, are able to support the development of other Online Communities of Practice, by utilizing modern technology and its mass dissemination.

Keywords: Online Community of Practice, Ubuntu, Online Learning

Introduction

Communities of Practice can be defined as a group of individuals or professionals who share a common passionate interest in a particular field of human endeavor, participate in a process of collective learning that creates bonds between them and choose voluntarily to deepen their knowledge and skills, through continuous interaction and dialogue (Wenger, 1998, 2009). Accordingly, Online Communities of Practice are «virtual spaces» within which their members interact, collaborate, learn from each other, co-create community spirit and offer sources of knowledge about a field of common interest (Hunter, 2001, Zhu & Baylen, 2005), while they are mainly, but not exclusively, formed through online interactions (Thang et al., 2011).

Ongoing commitment and collaboration between the members of Communities of Practice, create shared learning experiences that distinguish participants from non-participants (Wenger, 2011). Members of a group can create a Community of Practice by engaging meaningfully with each other, by holding each other accountable, and by sharing common practices (Thang et al., 2011). Communities of Practice place a higher value on collective knowledge than individual knowledge and they are characterized by environments of safety and trust (Johnson, 2001). In addition, the collaboration of stakeholders from different Communities of Practice to shape, analyze and solve a specific problem of common interest create Communities of Interest, which function as «communities of communities» (Brown & Duguid, 1991; Fischer, 2001). However, they differ from Communities of Practice due to their short duration, their informal character and their organic and not pre-designed development (Jones & Preece, 2006).

The Five-Stage Model

Various scientific models have been proposed to describe and analyze online communities of practice. One of the main ones is the Five-Stage Model (Salmon, 2000), which describes how participants in a community of practice can increase their knowledge and skills and create social networks, but also how their online supervisors can support them in this process (Salmon, 2013). A community of practice in its first stage provides incentives to its members and easy access to it. In the second stage, its members socialize with the other members and in the third stage they exchange information on their field of interest. In the fourth stage, they build new knowledge through interaction and in the fifth stage they develop an extroverted action that exceeds the boundaries of the community itself (Salmon, 2004). The Five-Stage Model, through its progressively evolving phases, constitutes a framework for the design and implementation of online learning (Moule, 2007), which allows both the online supervision of learning participants and the support of their individual development (Salmon, 2002).

Model Stages	Technical Skills	Online Supervision Activities
1. Access and provision of incentives	System setup and access	Welcome and encouragement
2. Online socialization	Sending and receiving messages	Familiarity and connection between cultural, social and learning environments
3. Exchange of information	Search and personalization	Facilitating projects and supporting the use of educational materials
4. Construction of knowledge	Conference	Facilitating procedures
5. Development	Providing links outside the community	Support and response

Table 1: The Five-Stage Model (Salmon, 2003)

The Greek Ubuntu Community

African tribal culture of teamwork has inspired the philosophy of many online software communities (Makoe & Shandu, 2019) and it has triggered the naming of the operating system Ubuntu (Raggi, Thomas, & Vugt, 2011), a free software, accessible without financial charge, whose functions and applications can be modified by any user and become again available to the rest of the users (Von Hagen, 2007). The name «Ubuntu» is derived from the expression of the African Xhosa tribe «Umuntu ngumntu ngabanye

abantu», which is interpreted as «each person's humanity is expressed through his ideal relationship with others» (Mabovula, 2011).

The community spirit philosophy of Ubuntu software is expressed through the feeling of love for the same object, but also through the feeling of freedom shared by its users (Fernandes, et al., 2019), which takes shape through the local online groups of software users (Ubuntu Local Community) in each region or country (Haines, 2017). However, as Ubuntu is based on non-windows Linux operating system, configuration and multitasking can become complex, which makes guidance of young users by the most skilled users of the community necessary (Sinha & Rajasingh, 2014).

The Greek Ubuntu Community is the only official and recognized Ubuntu community, by the Council of Ubuntu Local Teams, for Greece (Ubuntu Local Community Team Portal, 2016). In the official electronic magazine of the Greek community «Ubuntistas», an article entitled «How do I find solutions-answers to problems, wishes, questions» (2008) states that the community «consists of programmers, administrators, web-designers, but mainly ordinary users, who voluntarily participate in the creation - development - translation of the software, in the promotion and provision of support to other users. It works with self-organization and decisions in each project are made democratically by those who systematically contribute to it».

Community members' means of communication are mostly online. The official community website (<http://www.ubuntu-gr.org/>) was created in 2005, while the official community forum (<https://forum.ubuntu-gr.org/>) was created in 2008 and it numbers over 11.000 registered members. In 2011 the community's public group on Facebook platform was created (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/ubuntugr>) numbering over 8000 members, while since 2013 the videos on the official community channel on Youtube platform (<https://www.youtube.com/c/ubuntugr/>) exceed a total of 70.000 views.

Figure 1: The official community website

Characteristics of a Community of Practice

The Greek Ubuntu Community is a representative example of an Online Community of Practice in Greece, since it is a real community characterized by the common field of interest, on which its members exercise their practice. Its members form an authentic online community, with frequent interaction, participation, and effective collaboration. Several of its members have held live meetings developing a personal communication, while the official forum presents continuous operation and traffic.

A common area of community interest is the Ubuntu software. Although the members of the community may discuss topics related in general to Technology and Informatics, the axis around which the community is structured is the interest in the Ubuntu operating system and this is the motivation which pushes its members to reach out to it. The announcement of each new version (of distribution) of the operating system revives discussions in the forum and stands as an occasion for attracting new members to the community.

The community is also governed by specific characteristics, such as the common ideological background of its members, which consists of community spirit, immediacy in decision-making and the prominence of collectivities, which, through cooperation and self-organization, can compete with commercial software companies. This connecting link gives a different cohesion to the community and constant feedback of its motivations, which in turn achieve the attribution of honest and deeper meaning to the subject with which its members engage.

The present community, however, is not a simple community of interest, since its members, through personal experience, collaboration and real problem solving, build new knowledge on the specific cognitive object. At the same time, they optimize their methods, they teach and are taught on innovative technology approaches and they make their goals a reality, giving applicable solutions. In the forum, software user tutorials are built and stored, according to specific specifications and community members participate in the official team which translates the software into the Greek language, through the Launchpad platform (<https://launchpad.net/~ubuntu-110n-el>). At the same time, community members participate in autonomous Ubuntu support groups with personal web pages, which may exceed the narrow borders of Greece.

The Greek Ubuntu Community having all the characteristics of a typical Online Community of Practice can be analyzed using the respective analysis models of communities of practice. This analysis of the community characteristics is presented below, according to the Five-Stage Model, with data drawn from the official community forum.

Stage 1: Access and Provision of Incentives

Members of the Greek Ubuntu Community have access to it, with many ways and with different means of communication. The primary means of communication is provided through the official Community forum, which is structured into section. Each section refers to a broader category of interest that the user can refer to and that motivates active participation in a discussion. Examples of thematic sections are the general sections

«HARDWARE & DRIVERS», «SOFTWARE» and «UBUNTU IN EDUCATION «ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS, JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOLS, SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS, UNIVERSITIES)». A new member can be informed about how to use the forum from the section «Frequent Questions», and about the rules that govern it as well as about the actions of the Community from the thematic section «GREEK COMMUNITY UBUNTU-GR», which includes discussions such as «News - Announcements», «Events - Meetings - Actions & Promotion Material», «The Forum School - Asynchronous learning» and «Guides - How to – Tutorials».

Stage 2: Online Socialization

Adequate socialization of the community members and the development of a sense of «belonging» can be confirmed both by their recorded online communication, as well as from its emergence in their real-life encounters. Through the forum, all new members can refer to the discussion «Information and instructions to new entrants to the forum» in which they can learn about the rules governing member communication, as well as about hyperlinks of the social networks that they can utilize.

At the same time, the thematic subsection «About Winds» («Περί ανέμων») in which members can discuss any topic, includes conversations that aim to introduce all new members in the community and to give them the opportunity to fully introduce their interests and personality, joining a micro-society and forming an online identity. Such discussions are «To get to know each other...», «Favorite quotes – Quotations», «Which music track are you now listening to?», «Movies-Books» and «Happy Birthday». In the same direction also lies the existence of the «About Technology» discussion, where members, regardless of their technical training and experience, can discuss everyday technology issues and develop an initial and rudimentary interaction with the rest of the members.

Stage 3: Exchange of Information

Information sharing is a key part of the core of the Community, a fact which is reflected in more than thirty thousand discussion topics and in the thirty-five thousand posts by forum members. Information retrieval messages by the members are the subject of forum discussions, regarding problems encountered when trying to install and use Ubuntu software or regarding any other matter related to Technology. Examples of such discussions are the topics «problems with oem-kernel-cmdline (1.4kittyhawk7)», «Some help with task "C "», «.sh : command not found», «Ionic + Ubuntu phone app How do I build it in a package?», «Help for hacked Facebook account». Discussions and polls are also held to detect wider technical problems members are facing with the examined software, on topics such as «Passing to 18.04: How was it? (Includes Voting)».

Similarly, in the official Facebook group there are many posts, which receive corresponding feedback. Examples of extracts of such posts are the following: «Is there any free Greek-English/English-Greek dictionary for Linux?», «Do you know any app to lock folders in ubuntu 18.04», «How can I enable hibernation in ubuntu 18.10?», «the screen doesn't turn off when I don't use the laptop for, let's say, 10 minutes, like it did

before, the setting is normal (see photo)», «I don't know what and if it is to blame. Does maybe anyone know of anything I can try and implement? ». Thus, we observe a constant exchange of information, which directs members' effort and cooperation and acts as task instructions.

Stage 4: Construction of Knowledge

One of the great advantages of the way the forum is structured is its function as a place of production and repository of new knowledge. The basic generated knowledge of the Community refers to the use of the Ubuntu operating system and this can be expressed through bodies of text – «Guides», which analyze the correct way to use it. Members through coordinated procedures and methods, and via following defined steps, can create an electronic knowledge resource and of course they can have access to the existing ones.

In the thematic subsection «Guides - How to – Tutorials» members can have access to clear instructions on how they can create a basic and cognitively useful material, which, then, can be utilized educationally by the rest of the members. More specifically, discussions «How we create a complete guide (tutorial) for the forum», «Suggestions and general guiding discussions», «(Caution) Section guidelines and rules: Guides – Howto – Tutorials», «Guides - How to – Tutorials», «Ubuntu & UEFI -Installation – Documentation», «Ubuntu Beginner's Guide», «Ubuntu distribution upgrade tips». Similarly, we find thematic sections such as «Ubuntu-gr Marketing: How can I offer to the community», «Software Translations», «Found a translation error? Update here!», «The school of the Forum - Asynchronous Courses», «General Course Discussion – Suggestions», «Python Courses», «Terminal Courses», «Networking Courses» and many other corresponding subsections, which structure knowledge in an organized manner and have their own dynamics and online interaction.

Stage 5: Development

The accumulation of experience but also the creation of a critical mass of new knowledge was a starting point for community outreach and for member involvement in actions and groups that expand beyond its narrow boundaries, which indicates that it has mastered the stage of development, according to the Five-Stage Model. Community members have participated in various groups on Launchpad which is a web-based platform of collaborative management of team projects, while the participation of the members in actions of other groups and agencies, related to free software and Technology in general, was promoted. Such examples are recorded in thematic sections such as «Series of meetings on Opensource Hardware», «9th CIE2017 Conference, University of Piraeus», «Ubuntu Marketing Greek Team - Sign Up! », «Ubuntu community seminar in PaPei», «Discussion on creating a radio station Ubuntu-gr», «Promoting linux/technology to non-technical people/our acquaintances», «Facebook pages, groups, and apps».

Outgoing community actions, however, declined drastically after 2017, according to the recorded participation in the corresponding thematic discussions, which leads us to the conclusion that the community is no longer maintained in the development stage.

Nowadays, the online presence of the community is limited to translating, distributing, or modifying each new release of the Ubuntu operating system, and active discussion topics are largely related to these actions. The thematic sub-section «News - Announcements» as well as the general discussions on Technology have a corresponding frequency of posts.

A transition from the systematic use of the forum as a means of organizing the new knowledge, to the use of the public Facebook group for extracting information or for updates, due to the immediacy of social media, but also to its accessibility, to non-technically specialized or occasional community members. This transition allows the fastest members' response to a request for technical assistance, but it is not marked by a corresponding solid structure, which promotes the creation of new knowledge.

Conclusions

Online Communities of Practice are characterized by the common field in which their members practice, by interacting through the Internet. This interaction leads to solution of real problems and construction of new knowledge. The Greek Ubuntu Community is a clear example of this online community. To analyze its characteristics, the Five Stage Model was used and it was found that the structure and development of the Greek Ubuntu Community can be accurately captured with the above model.

From the analysis of the online presence of the community, it is found that although the examined community passed through all the stages of a Community of Practice and evolved to the last stage of development, finally it was not preserved in this, but again it moved to the previous stage of construction of knowledge, according to the Five Stage Model. Also, of critical importance is the overindulgence of the use of the forum over the use of social media, as a tool for communication and interaction of the members in the specific online community of practice, a fact which has a decisive effect on the way of building new knowledge and on overall online learning.

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